

MAGNETO-CHEMICAL STUDIES IN VALENCY. PART VI. BOND-TYPE AND STEREOCHEMISTRY OF FOUR-COORDINATED COPPER COMPLEXES

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The magnetic susceptibility of a large number of copper compounds has been measured both at the room temperature and also, in a few cases, at low temperatures (-13° to -190°) for the purpose of θ -correction. From a comparison of the moment values, particularly after θ -correction, it has been shown that the 4-coordinated copper complexes can be divided into two groups: one with moment values lying between 1.72 and 1.82 Bohr and the other with values between 1.90 and 2.20 Bohr. The division, though not always a very sharp one, is still quite significant. It is, therefore, suggested that in the former the bond is homopolar of the dsp^2 planar square type and in the latter it is either ionic or covalent of the tetrahedral sp^3 or planar sp^3d type. The lower moment value of the first group results from more or less complete quenching of the orbital moment of the single unpaired electron raised to the outermost $4p$ level of the atom, where it is fully exposed to the electric field of the neighbouring atoms and ions, away from the nucleus screened by the co-ordinating electrons. This difference in moment value serves to distinguish between the two types of copper complexes, the penetration and the associated ones, though, in both, the central copper atom contains one unpaired electron. It is also significant to note that all those complexes with lower moment values (1.72-1.82) are either black, brown, red, greenish yellow or violet-blue, while others with higher moment values are green, blue or blue-violet. A relationship between the colour and the bond type or structure of the complex is thereby suggested, as in the corresponding nickel complexes.

It is now well known that the determination of magnetic moment serves as a very useful means for studying the nature of the bond and the configuration of a co-ordination complex, particularly in the case of transitional elements like iron, cobalt, nickel and silver. This magneto-chemical method of study has gained special significance since the development of the quantum mechanical theory of co-ordination compounds by Pauling (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1367, 3225). For, in the case of complexes with any of the above-mentioned elements furnishing the central atom, a profound alteration in the magnetic properties of the latter is observed according as the bond involved in the formation of the complex is ionic or covalent; and according to Pauling's theory, this is closely related to the structure of the complex molecule as well. But in the case of trivalent chromium and bivalent copper no apparent difference in the magnetic properties is predicted by the theory. A consideration of the electronic structure of the simple cupric and nickelous ions, as well as of their atoms in four-coordinated complexes on the basis of this theory, makes it clear.

From the electronic configuration shown above it will be found that the theory postulates the occurrence of two types of co-ordination complexes differing in structure, viz., tetrahedral (sp^3 bonds) and planar square (dsp^2 bonds). Of these, the electronic configuration of the central atom of the tetrahedral complexes remains undisturbed as in their simple ions. Consequently, the bonds may resonate with the ionic type, and the magnetic moment of the central atom becomes undistinguishable from that of the

	Argon shell	3d	4s	4p	4d	
Cu ⁺⁺	18		—	—	—	
Do (complex tetrahedral)	"					<i>sp³ bond</i>
Do (complex planar)	"					<i>ds²sp² bond</i>
"	"					<i>sp²d bond</i>
Ni ⁺⁺	"		—	—	—	
Do (complex tetrahedral)	"					<i>sp³ bond</i>
Do (complex planar)	"					<i>ds²sp² bond</i>

corresponding ion. This is amply borne out by experimental results. In the case of square nickel complexes with ds^2 bonds, all the nickel electrons become paired, with the result that the substances become diamagnetic and are thus sharply distinguished from the simple nickel ion or its tetrahedral complexes, as these latter contain two unpaired electrons. In the case of copper, however, both the tetrahedral and planar complexes contain one unpaired electron like the simple copper ion. Hence, their magnetic properties should, on this consideration, be practically identical. In fact, all copper complexes, as well as the simple cupric ion, show a moment value of 1.73–2.20 Bohr magnetons. This approaches more or less the theoretical values of $1.73 \mu_B$ for one unpaired electron on the basis of Heise-Stoner's formula. But on a close examination, it will be found that in the square copper complexes the unpaired electron is promoted to a higher level, $4p$, whereas in the simple cupric ion and its tetrahedral complexes it occurs in the $3d$ -level. It is believed that this is likely to produce a slight but measurable difference in the magnetic moment between the tetrahedral and square complexes. Pauling, in fact, suggested that the moment value of the square copper complexes should be slightly lower than that of its simple ion and tetrahedral complexes, because of the greater quenching effect of the more unsymmetrical field of the attached groups in the former upon the residual orbital moment (Pauling, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond," 1940, p. 141). For the moment of the cupric ion in solution (1.95–2.20)

is always higher than the theoretical value of $1.73\mu_B$ on the basis of Bose-Stoner's formula, due to small contribution by the orbital moment. But it might also be pointed out that in the square complexes, the lone unpaired electron, being removed to a higher level and screened off by the co-ordinated electron-pairs of the attached groups, is less influenced by the nuclear field of the central atom; consequently, the perturbing and quenching effect of the field of the neighbouring atoms and ions on its orbital moment will be more in evidence. Both the above-mentioned factors might, however, be expected to make their contribution to this end. Hence, the moment value of the square copper complexes (ds^2 bonds) will approach more closely to the theoretical value of $1.73\mu_B$ than is the case with its tetrahedral complexes or the simple cupric ion. Pauling (*loc. cit.*) has quoted moment values of certain four-coordinated copper complexes which, on the basis of X-ray analysis, are known to possess planar square configuration. But, these instances are unconvincing, and the quoted moment values are of rather doubtful nature. For, these include substances like $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$, etc., and the moment values quoted for them are stated to lie between 1.79 and 1.87 as reported by some workers. But others (Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 164) including ourselves have obtained different and higher moment values for the substances mentioned. Moreover, all chemical and electrochemical considerations lead to the inevitable conclusion that the bonds in these compounds are definitely of the ionic type. The substances like $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are known to undergo more or less complete dissociation in aqueous solution, giving all the reactions characteristic of simple cupric ions. The planar structure for these molecules, as determined by the X-ray analysis, cannot be regarded as an undoubted evidence about their covalent character. For, as is well known, even the ionic compounds in the crystalline state may give rise to planar configuration, if the radius ratio and the polarization properties of the ions lie within certain limits (cf. Goldschmidt, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 267). Besides, as the ionic bond may resonate with both tetrahedral sp^3 and planar sp^2d bonds (with d -orbital in the same valence shell as s and p), the planar structure found for the above-mentioned copper complexes might as well be attributed to weak covalent bonds of the sp^2d type. These bonds are, therefore, described by some as semi-polar and semi-covalent bonds. The compounds with such bonds, therefore, are to be placed in the class of associated complexes.

An essentially planar covalent structure for a molecule must retain its character unchanged even in solutions. Hence, the conclusion drawn from the X-ray examination alone cannot be the sole criterion for the bond type in complexes.

It was, therefore, expected that a careful magnetic measurement of copper complexes might throw some light on the bond type in these molecules, though not with as much uniqueness as in the case of nickel complexes. With this end in view the measurement of magnetic moment of a large number of copper complexes was undertaken, and the variation of magnetic moment with temperature was also determined in some cases for the sake of exact comparison after allowing for the θ -correction. A few compounds, the moment values of which have been determined by other workers, have also been included in order to make the list as comprehensive as possible.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The preparation of all the copper complexes under investigation was made with chemically pure substances and the purity of the products was ascertained by the determination of their copper content. The magnetic susceptibility at room temperature of these complexes was measured in a Gouy's balance with a field strength of 10.16×10^5 gauss, taking all the usual precautions described in previous communications. Measurement of susceptibilities at low temperatures was carried out in a special quartz torsion balance using a cryostat of the gas-flow type in which the supply of cold air and liquid air was adjusted by the working of a pump controlled by the automatic operation of a sensitive relay. Temperature in the cryostat could be maintained constant within 1° . The entire apparatus consisting of the torsion balance and the cryostatic arrangement was designed by Dr. A. Bose for his measurements of magnetic properties of paramagnetic crystals at low temperatures at the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science. A detailed description of the apparatus and its working has been published in the Science Congress Proceedings (1949, Part III, 41). We express our thanks to Dr. A. Bose and Mr. A. Datta for kindly measuring the susceptibilities of some of our substances at low temperatures.

In calculating the magnetic moment for the copper atom in the complex, diamagnetic corrections were made in each case. For susceptibilities of atoms and various structural constants, Pascal's values (corrected) were employed. For ions, the susceptibility values given by Trew (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1941, **37**, 488) were used. The diamagnetic correction for bivalent copper was assumed to be equal to that of bivalent zinc as their ionic radii are almost equal. The values for the latter, as given by Kido (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1933, **21**, 149, 288), is -12.8×10^{-6} . The moment value of the central copper atom is then calculated from the expression, $\mu_s = 2.84 \sqrt{\chi_s \cdot T}$, and from $2.84 \sqrt{\chi_s \cdot (T - \theta)}$ where θ -correction was available from the measurement of susceptibility variation with temperature. The values of θ was obtained by plotting the values of $1/\chi_s$ against the absolute temperature, the intercept of the curve on the temperature co-ordinate giving the value of θ .

D I S C U S S I O N

On arranging the substances under investigation as in the following table with their colours, values of their magnetic moments, and their crystal structure, wherever known, against each, we find that an interesting classification of the complexes into two groups emerges from, an analysis of their moment values, more or less in good agreement with their physico-chemical behaviour. The compounds No. 1-17, which are presumably inner-metallic complexes of the penetration type, as revealed by their chemical behaviour, show magnetic moment values closer to the spin moment of one unbalanced electron ($1.73 \mu_B$), particularly when the θ -correction is made. These values, after θ -correction where it has been made, lie more or less between 1.66 and $1.81 \mu_B$. The remaining compounds, particularly after θ -correction, show more or less an effective moment value of 1.90 to $2.20 \mu_B$. To this group belong all the copper ethylenediamine

TABLE I
Results of magnetic measurement.

Substance.	Colour.	%Cu.	t in °K.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_A \times 10^6$.	μ_B .	μ_B corrected for θ .	Remarks.
1. Copper biguanide chloride [Cu(C ₂ H ₅ N ₃) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Rose-red	17.04 calc. 17.06	305	3.249	1204	-131	1335	1.73 $\theta=27$	
2. Copper diethylbiguanide Cu(C ₂ H ₅ N ₃) ₂	Rose-red (1) Violet-blue (2)	16.93 16.85 calc. 16.91	304 304	2.685 2.813	1009 1058	-190 -190	1199 1248	1.66 1.72 $\theta=10$	
3. Copper dimethylglyoxime Cu(C ₂ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂) ₂	Dark brown	21.50 calc. 21.66	314	4.276	1255	-108.7	1353.7	1.80 $\theta=8$	
4. Copper picolinate Cu(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂	Violet-blue	20.55 calc. 20.67	299	4.089	1258	-133	1391	1.84 $\theta=37$	Planer (Cox, J. Chem. Soc., 1935, 731; 1936, 775)
5. Copper metaphenylene dibiguanide chloride [Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₁₀)Cl ₂ ·1.5H ₂ O	Red-violet	14.63 calc. 14.53	304	2.640	1150	-169.5	1319.5	1.80 $\theta=30$	
6. Copper biguanide thiocyanate [Cu(C ₂ H ₅ N ₃) ₂](SCN) ₂	Blue-violet	16.67 calc. 16.63	303	3.206	1223	-125	1348	1.82	
7. Copper phenylbiguanide chloride [Cu(C ₂ H ₅ N ₃) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Red	11.74 calc. 11.72	302	2.018	1095	-249	1344	1.81	

TABLE I (contd.)
Results of magnetic measurement.

Substance.	Colour.	%Cu.	t in °K.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_A \times 10^6$.	μ_B .	μ_B corrected for θ .	Remarks.
8. Copper dicyan- diamidine $Cu(C_2H_3N_3O)_2$	Rose-red.	24.04 calc. 23.93	304	4.614	1225	-74	1299	1.78	
9. Copper ethylene- diamine bisacetylaceton $Cu(C_{12}H_{18}N_4O_2)$	Dark violet	22.13 calc. 22.26	305	4.097	1169	-129	1298	1.78	
10. Copper benzoin monoxime $Cu(C_{12}H_{11}NO_3)$	Green	21.90 calc. 22.02	296	3.978	1148	-137.5	1285.5	1.76	
11. Copper phenylbi- guanide <i>p</i> -sulphonate $Cu(C_8H_{10}N_6O_8S)_2$	Violet-red	10.64 calc. 10.71	303	1.793	1064	-219	1283	1.77	
12. Copper phthal- cyanine $Cu(C_8H_4N_2)$	Dark blue			1.68	966	-251	1217	1.73 (K)	Planar (Robert- son, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1935, 615; 1936, 1195; 1937, 219).
13. bis-Salicylaldehyde propylenediamine copper $Cu(C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_4)$	Violet							1.76 (M)	
14. Copper ethylene dibiguanide sulphate $[Cu(C_6H_8N_6)]SO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$	Rose-red	14.64 calc. 14.70	300	2.818	1219	-148	1397	1.82	

TABLE I (contd.)
Results of magnetic measurements

Substance.	Colour.	%Cu.	t in °K.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	$\bar{\chi}_M \times 10^6$.	$\delta \times 10^6$.	$\chi_A \times 10^6$.	μ_B .	θ in °K. μ_B (corr.)	Remarks
15. Copper salicylaldehyde $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2$	Yellowish green	18.90 calc. 18.94	303	3.690	1238	-146	1384	1.84		Planar (Cox., <i>loc. cit.</i>)
16. Copper oxine $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO})_2$	Dirty yellow	18.02 calc. 18.08	302	3.499	1230	-179	1409	1.85	15	1.81
17. Copper cystin $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Pale green	18.66 calc. 18.84	300	3.699	1262	-172.5	1434.5	1.86	-7	1.89
18. Copper bispyridine thiocyanate $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2] (\text{SCN})_2$	Violet-blue	18.81 calc. 18.84	305.6	3.807	1285	-158	1443	1.89	35	1.77
19. Copper bisformyl camphor $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2)_2$	Grass green							1.89 (M)		
20. Copper sulphaniolate $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NSO}_2)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dark green	13.22 calc. 13.25	297	2.777	1331	-219	1550	1.93	15	1.91
21. Copper phenyl- glyoxime $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NO}_2)_2$	Blue	17.46 calc. 17.48	298	3.653	1327	-178	1505	1.92		
22. Potassium cupric chloride $\text{K}_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blue	19.99 calc. 19.89	305	4.217	1355	-157	1512	1.93 1.87 (S)	-8	1.95
23. Copper bispyridine nitrate $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Blue	18.35 calc. 18.46	300	4.047	1308	-138	1536	1.93		
24. Copper anthranilate $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N})_2$	Green	18.94 calc. 18.95	303	4.115	1381	-152	1533	1.93	10	1.92

M=Meillon (J.
Proc. Roy. Soc.
N. S. Wales
1942, 18, 138.

Planar
S=Sugden,
loc. cit.

TABLE I (contd.)

Results of magnetic measurements

Substance.	Colour.	%Cu.	t in °K.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\delta \times 10^6$.	$\chi_A \times 10^6$.	μ_B .	θ in °K μ_B (corr.).	Remarks.
25. Copper quinaldine 8-carboxylate $Cu(C_{10}H_6O_2N)_2 \cdot H_2O$	Light blue	14.92 calc. 14.94	305	3.116	1344	-213	1537	1.93		
26. Copper quinaldinate $Cu(C_{10}H_6O_2N)_2 \cdot H_2O$	Green	14.83 calc. 14.94	301	3.148	1304	-212.5	1552.5	1.94		
27. Copper bisethylenediamine thiocyanate $[Cu(C_2H_8N_2)_2](SCN)_2$	Blue-violet	18.88 calc. 18.95	303	4.065	1366	-171	1537	1.94		
28. Copper tetrapyridine nitrate $[Cu(C_5H_5N)_4](NO_3)_2$	Blue-violet	12.55 calc. 12.62	303	2.572	1298	-251	1549	1.94		
29. Copper dimethylglyoxime chloride $[Cu(C_2H_5O_2N_2)_2]Cl_2$	Bright green	25.36 calc. 25.38	303	5.753	1442	-103	1545	1.94	-85	2.2
30. Potassium cupri-salicylate $K_2[Cu(C_{12}H_8O_4)_2] \cdot 4H_2O$	Green	13.08 calc. 13.10	305	2.637	1280	-223.6	1503.6	1.93	0	1.93
31. Copper glycine $[Cu(C_2H_5NO_2)_2] \cdot H_2O$	Deep blue	27.30 calc. 27.46	303	6.228	1430	-97	1527	1.93	-100	2.2
32. Copper tetrammine nitrate $[Cu(NH_3)_4](NO_3)_2$	Blue							2.0		Stoner "Magnetism and Matter", 1934, P. 493.
33. bis-Formylcamphor ethylenediamine copper dihydrate $Cu(C_{14}H_{18}O_2N_2)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Wine-red							2.08		Mellor (loc. cit.)

K = Klemm, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1935, 143, 82; 1939, 164, 73.
M = Mellor, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc. N. S. Wales*, 1942, 76, 158.

complexes, copper pyridine complexes, potassium cupric chloride, copper dimethylglyoxime chloride and a few others, which are often regarded as inner metallic complexes, such as copper sulphanilate, copper anthranilate, copper quinaldinate, copper quinaldine 8-carboxylate, copper glycine and copper phenylglycine, etc. Thus, as already referred to in the theoretical part, a distinction between the copper complexes with dsp^2 planar square bonds and those with ionic, sp^3 tetrahedral or sp^2d planar bonds is possible, in spite of the fact that in both types of complexes the paramagnetism of the substance results from the presence of one unpaired electron in the system. The former represents complexes of the penetration type and the latter those of the associated class.

It might be pointed out here that there is yet no evidence for the tetrahedral structure even in the solid state for 4-coordinated copper complexes. All the cupric complexes of either the penetration or the associated type that have yet been examined, are planar. Hence, the bonds in these copper complexes are either of dsp^2 square covalent type, or sp^2d planar feebly covalent type, or predominantly ionic in character. This distinction, though deducible in a general way from their physico-chemical properties, becomes more or less conspicuous from a comparison of their magnetic properties. For instance, copper glycine and copper phenylglycine, which belong to the group of inner-metallic complexes, do not differ much in their physical and chemical properties and in the nature of their co-ordination from copper cystine; but the magnetic measurements show that in the latter the bonds are strongly covalent of the planar dsp^2 type, whereas in the former two they are weakly covalent of the planar sp^2d type, resonating with the ionic structure to a certain extent. This difference may possibly be attributed to the fact that cystine behaves as a four-coordinating or quadrifunctional unit.

There appears to be another significant distinction between these two classes of copper complexes, which expresses itself in their difference of colour. All those cupric complexes in which the bond is predominantly ionic, ion-dipole, or of feebly covalent type (sp^2d or sp^3), *i. e.* all those which are described as normal or associated complexes, are either deep blue, blue, blue-violet, or green in colour; whereas those in which the bond is strongly covalent of the dsp^2 type, classed as penetration complexes, show quite a variety of colours such as red, rose-red, violet-red, violet, greenish yellow, dark brown, and intense dark blue with metallic lustre. The blue colour is thus found in both the groups, whereas red, rose-red, dark brown, yellowish green or greenish yellow are confined only to the strong covalent complexes of the dsp^2 type, described as the penetration complexes. The *bis*-formylcamphor ethylenediamine copper dihydrate, which is wine-red in colour but gives an effective moment value of $2.08 \mu_B$ according to Mellor (*J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales, 1942, 75, 168*), seems to form the only exception to this. A redetermination of the susceptibility value of this compound in a magnetically pure form and of its temperature variation might possibly lead to a revision of the moment value. This colour distinction in the case of copper complexes, however, is not so sharp as in the corresponding nickel compounds. This is in close agreement with their magnetic distinction. For, as is well known, the two types of nickel complexes, penetration and associated, are clearly distinguished by their opposite magnetic character, the former being diamagnetic with red, yellow or brown colour, and the latter being paramagnetic, with blue or blue-violet colour.

A few individual cases deserve special consideration. The copper benzoin monoxime contains one copper atom for one molecule of benzoin monoxime. Its structure is represented by many by the configuration (I) in which the copper atom is assumed to form rather unusual co-ordination bonds with phenyl groups. The effective moment value of the compound corresponds exactly to the spin moment of one unpaired electron. It resembles in this respect the anhydrous cupric halides, indicating the presence of covalent bonds in four-fold co-ordination. The compound may, therefore, be represented with advantage by the configuration (II) in which the molecule is associated in the form of an unending chain like the anhydrous palladous chloride, the two oxygen atoms of each molecule with their lone pair of electrons supplying the necessary points for co-ordination or attachment with the copper atom of the adjoining molecule.

(I)

(II)

The configuration (II) may have either a *cis* or a *trans* arrangement of oxygen and nitrogen atoms around the central copper atom.

Copper sulphaniolate, on the other hand, presents a case in which the bond must be regarded either as purely ionic, or, we may assume, as in the previous case, an unending co-ordinated chain structure of associated molecules. The bonds in the latter case, as the magnetic moment shows, will be necessarily of the weak covalent character of sp^2d type. The structure is represented by the configuration (III), which may also be of two isomeric types, *cis* and *trans*, assuming a planar arrangement.

(III)